

**Binary Representation in String Theory:
A Thought Experiment into 1s and 0s**

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Date Completed: 15th July, 2024

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to delve into the world of quantum mechanics and string theory and try to represent its system using only binary digits in a model as a thought experiment, looking at the field from a different perspective to really theorise what a string could be fundamentally. This paper is not meant to replace any existing models and will focus on the possible interactions and implications of existing laws of the universe. In this paper, we try to represent strings as binary digits, albeit with a few changes to their structure to be as accurate as possible in the complex world of quantum mechanics. For simplicity, we added a “-1” to represent dark energy being a sort of equilibrium in space due to its abundance and fluctuations happening in its presence. This means we use 1s, 0s, and -1s as an even more fundamental unit, being composed of energy. 1 being the presence of a high amount of energy, and 0 being the presence of a low amount of energy. These numbers are then put into a matrix, which we then finally call a string, with each bit inside responsible for its average frequency. This is an extremely simplified way to look at how strings could be able to interact in the quantum realm, which will be lacking in complete accuracy and proof. We made a few assumptions based on our current understanding of the universe, which will have no mathematical proof to support it, primarily that dark energy is the “equilibrium” since there’s no proof that it is or isn’t. This paper is meant to be an introduction before getting into the more accurate equations already established years prior.

Introduction

Quantum Mechanics, known for its complexity and ability to give anyone inexperienced a headache, and String Theory, known for being controversial in the physics community due to inadequate evidence of it being true. Now what would happen if a paper came along and tried to represent String Theory into binary digits with some modifications? The following paper will cover these topics: String theory, binary digits, Dark energy, an attempt of creating a model, and a conclusion.

String Theory

According to Greene, B. (June, 2024); String Theory aims to combine the general theory of relativity by Albert Einstein with quantum mechanics. Rather than being treated as zero-dimensional point particles, as is more common, subatomic particles are instead modelled as tiny one-dimensional "stringlike" entities, hence the name string theory. A string experiencing a specific mode of vibration is equivalent to a particle having specific characteristics like mass and charge. Scientists discovered in the 1980s that string theory might be the long-awaited unified field theory since it could unite all forms of matter and the four forces of nature: gravity, electromagnetism, strong force, and weak force, into a single quantum mechanical framework. Even though string theory is still an active field of study and is developing quickly, it is still fundamentally a mathematical concept because it hasn't been verified by experimental observations.

Binary Digits

I believe most people would have an idea what binary digits are, but for those who don't, binary digits, or "bits," are commonly used in computers to relay information, consisting of two states: '0' as in a low voltage (off), and '1' as in a high voltage (on). These bits come in different amounts depending on the system, e.g., 32-bit, 64-bit, etc. One bit may not convey a lot of information with only 2 possible states, but 2 bits raise the number to 4, and 3 bits will have 8 possibilities; the number of possibilities rises exponentially. Here is a graph to illustrate this:

Amount of Combinations per Bit

Dark Energy and Dark matter

Not much is known about dark energy with many unconfirmed theories, but according to Riess, A. (May, 2024); Dark energy, a gravitationally repulsive force, is the dominant component of the universe, accounting for 69.4% of its mass. Dark energy is detected by its impact on the rate of universe expansion and large-scale structure formation. Its dominance has led to faster expansion rates than in the past. The oldest explanation of dark energy is a vacuum energy

density inherent to empty space. This energy density, equivalent to Einstein's cosmological constant, arises naturally from quantum fluctuations in empty space. Probabilistic solutions, motivated by string theory, explain the discrepancy. Another theory suggests that dark energy is a transient vacuum energy resulting from the potential energy of a dynamical field. It is known as "quintessence" and varies in space and time, distinguishing it from a cosmological constant. It is similar in mechanism but vastly different in scale to the scalar field energy in the inflationary theory of the big bang. Another possible explanation may be attributed to topological defects in the universe's fabric, such as cosmic strings or walls. The production of new defects as the universe expands is mathematically similar to a cosmological constant, but the equation of state for these defects depends on whether they are strings (**1-D**) or walls (**2-D**).

According to CERN (n.d.); unlike normal matter, dark matter does not interact with the electromagnetic force. This means it does not absorb, reflect or emit light, making it extremely hard to spot. In fact, researchers have been able to infer the existence of dark matter only from the gravitational effect it seems to have on visible matter. Dark matter seems to outweigh visible matter roughly six to one, making up about 27% of the universe.

The Model

Now that you have a general basis in string theory and binary digits, we will now begin to cover the actual model one step at a time, with an added summary at the end of it.

The Format of a String

Let's try to use a matrix to define a string. We will borrow a concept from matrices, using the brackets '[' and ']' to begin the string "[]". And use a comma to separate its elements. e.g., **[1, 0, 1]**

Zeros and Ones

Defining '0' and '1' for string theory doesn't make sense at the surface since they are fixed values with only an "on" or "off" state, which goes against what quantum mechanics says with its uncertainty principle. How do we know if it will only stay in that state? Wouldn't the 0s and 1s make it predictable? To solve this, we must consider a different approach. A direct translation of binary to string theory would be '0' meaning the absence of a vibration, and '1' would mean the presence of a vibration. Which, as stated before, will not suffice. Let's instead, define '1' as a higher probability of a certain vibration (whatever it may be) and '0' as a lower probability of a vibration. That way, we incorporate probability into the model.

A '1' will simply be the presence of energy, and '0' will be the "absence" of energy. '0' is problematic, as it would mean a string is a combination of energy and the absence of energy.

There are three possibilities.

- **a)** '0' is the absence of energy, but some law of the universe allows it to interact with energy to create a string. (Relies on our lack of knowledge of every law of the universe.)
- **b)** '0' is a different kind of energy we haven't discovered yet due to its lack of effects. (Relies on our lack of knowledge about different kinds of energy, especially dark energy.)
- **c)** '0' is energy but contains "less" compared to a '1'. (Relies purely on energy.)

We can remove 'a' from consideration. Since a string will vibrate at different frequencies, we will consider it a wave, so a section of the wave with no energy at all can be ruled out. 'b' is certainly possible, as they may be a kind of energy we haven't discovered yet, but it's hard to support it. 'c' seems more likely as the frequency will have certain "parts" with more or less energy at random, so '0' containing less energy but still being energy itself will have a lower frequency (technically "amplitude") but can occasionally increase in intensity. Giving the string its "randomness" seen everywhere in quantum mechanics. For the rest of the paper, we will only consider 'c'.

Connection with Dark Energy and Dark Matter

Let's take inspiration from a concept known as quantum fluctuations, where a seemingly "empty" area suddenly has energy when matter and antimatter are created and "cancel" each other out immediately, releasing a gamma ray in the process. According to string theory, matter (and antimatter) are from strings, so for the purposes of our model, we will be using this "dark energy" and "dark matter" as a sort of "balanced" state in space due to their abundance in space. Why dark matter? Because if we observe "regular" matter (the one we are familiar with), it is actually just energy as mass from the equation $e = mc^2$ (^ is to signify an exponent). Although dark matter isn't necessarily connected to dark energy, we can see from the difference in mass and energy that both exhibit different properties but are fundamentally connected, so hence we can assume that dark matter and dark energy are connected in some way (no matter how small it may be).

We will be representing dark matter and dark energy as a ‘-1’ Now the ‘-’ doesn’t necessarily mean that it is the opposite of ‘1’ (although it very well could be), so we can model “empty space” as “[**-1, -1, -1, -1, -1, ...**]” for however long you want. Now, unlike a string, this “empty space” is not **1-D** and is not limited to just the **3-D** world, so we can give it more depth. To illustrate the “levels,” we will use ‘1.’ and increment by one per “line” for **2-D** representation in matrices which could yield results like this: (Note: use ‘;’ to separate lines.)

1. [-1, -1, -1, -1, -1, ...]; **2.** [-1, -1, ... , 0, 1, 0, 1, 1, ..., -1, -1, ...]; **3.** [-1, -1, -1, -1, -1...]; ...

As you can see, we are now representing the **2-D** world with the model, with line 2 containing a string “surrounded” by dark energy. We are currently not accounting for time, but that will appear later on. (Note: a “set” with only ‘-1’ will be called a “dark set.”)

The Interactions of the String

Now that we have defined the “parts” of the string, we shall move on to the interactions of strings. Let’s move on to the interesting stuff one by one.

Creation of the string

As stated before, we’re borrowing a concept from quantum fluctuations: for a string to be formed, it must also create another string that has the opposite property (it doesn’t necessarily mean the frequency is the opposite, but it will have opposite properties). This means that in a system, the number of strings should always be even (for the whole universe, not just the local system). This doesn’t account for the strings that formed due to the big bang; this is still a major

question in the universe, as why would there be more matter than antimatter if, for matter to form, antimatter would also have to form for equilibrium? It only focuses on the fluctuations. E.g., [0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, ...] and [1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1, ...] could have different properties but aren't necessary "opposites," but when "combined," they will "cancel," releasing a gamma ray in the process. The '+' operator will be used to add strings (which will cancel them out).

As in [0, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, ...] + [1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1, ...] = [?, ?, ?, ...] when cancelled, a byproduct will be created from it. (Note: We won't define the length of a string since it might as well be infinity to us due to the complexity and frequencies present; an insane amount would be needed to accurately make one.)

Creation of a Particle

When multiple strings form, they can group together (not combine) and form a particle. From our definition of the string, this in theory would mean that there are infinitely different particles in the universe, but luckily we can say that those particles that don't exist are unstable enough that they either don't form at all or separate instantaneously. Existing particles, though, will be made by the strings with the correct or similar (on average) frequency. Due to their unstable frequencies and probability, the string itself would have to have the right frequency at the right time with others to form a particle, which in turn would allow the string that appears with it to go into the antiparticle instead.

Now the operator used to group strings will be ‘|’ in between strings.

E.g., $[1, 0, 1, 1, 0, \dots] | [1, 0, 0, 1, 1, \dots] | [1, 0, 1, 1, 1, \dots] = ([1, 0, 1, 1, 0, \dots]; [1, 0, 0, 1, 1, \dots]; [1, 0, 1, 1, 1, \dots])$ A group uses parentheses ‘(’ and ‘)’ and uses a semicolon ‘;’ to separate strings in the group.

Interactions of the particle

Now we have a particle and an antiparticle, but how do they interact? When a particle and antiparticle combine (denoted with ‘+’ just like strings), they release a gamma ray (γ).

E.g. $([1, 0, 1, 1, 0, \dots]; [1, 0, 0, 1, 1, \dots]; [1, 0, 1, 1, 1, \dots]) +$

$([0, 1, 1, 0, 0, \dots]; [0, 0, 1, 0, 1, \dots]; [0, 0, 1, 1, 0, \dots]) = \gamma$

The strings inside the particles will combine with their counterparts and cancel out; in the end, the result is a gamma ray being released.

Model in Different Dimensions

We have covered what it could be like in **1-D** and **2-D** (1 string or a dark set; multiple strings or/and dark sets into a plane), but what would it be like in the higher dimensions?

3-Dimensional

Let's start with the most intuitive one, which is after **2-D** and **3-D**. Now all we have to do is just add another variable in a different direction, so now we get something like this:

1A. [-1, ...]; 1B. [-1, ...]; 1C. [-1, ...]; ...
 2A. [-1, ...]; 2B. [0, 1, 0, ...]; 2C. [-1, ...]; ...
 3A. [-1, ...]; 3B. [-1, ...]; 3C. [-1, ...]; ...
 ...

Now we have something like a cube, the difference being that the "length" of this particular cube is finite but could be extremely long since one 'bit' would be extremely small, so there'll be a lot. This is the same case for **1-D**, as one string is already going to be long. However, since this is now **3-D**, we also have to account for its depth (noted by the letters 'A' to 'C' in the example). You can see at **2B**, a string is present surrounded by the dark sets (the 'dark sets' aren't actually sets; each '-1' is independent from each other, but for simplicity, we will call it a set). If we were only looking from a **2-D** perspective, we wouldn't have seen any other letters except 'A'. The depth is finite and more manageable than the seemingly "infinite" length.

4-Dimensional

Now this is where things start to get tricky. First off, what is the fourth dimension? There are 2 interpretations: **1)** 3-dimensional space with time as another dimension; and **2)** 4-dimensional space without a "time dimension." What would that mean?

The first interpretation is what is usually first thought of when one hears “**4-D**,” but what does a **4-D** actually mean? Using the first interpretation, would a **3-D** universe therefore be a **2-D universe** with time? The simple answer is yes. The first interpretation would mean that a dimension should include one “time” dimension in it, so if **2-D** is **1-D** with time, what is **1-D**? **1-D** could mean two things: one spatial dimension or one time dimension. Now we have universes with only space or time and not both.

Universes with only one spatial dimension or one time dimension

Let’s tackle the simplest possibility: a universe in only **1-T** (one time dimension) would simply not exist; there’s no space for it to occupy and thus wouldn’t appear, or if it does, would instantly be with the rest of the **0-D** void. The **0-D** void would be the vast “emptiness” of the “multiverse”; the distances of each universe contained within would be far beyond human comprehension but, in theory, aren’t infinite but could approach it with time, causing the universes to get further apart or not change in distance at all from each other.

Now for the universes with only one spatial dimension, it gets a little trickier. Assume a **1-D** universe is created starting with the size of $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0}$, where x is the “length” of the universe.

Remember, we are dealing with one spatial dimension, where under normal conditions, with time, it will continuously expand its length; in this case, there’s no time. Which would mean that it would start as infinitely small and will never expand since there’s no time for it to expand.

Mathematical 4-D and More

Another interpretation for **4-D** is the mathematical concept of just spatial dimensions; we already use this interpretation for many diagrams when talking about **3-D** and **2-D** objects.

Simply add another direction in the diagram, so **x**, **y**, and **z**, and another variable to represent it.

This comes with ignoring time or at least not counting it as a dimension; one could look at it by taking a time frame of a dimension in the first interpretation, so **4-D** (3-D and 1-T) would be **3-D** here. This works for the higher dimensions as well.

Higher dimensions

For the higher dimensions, we will be using the first interpretation since the second one is already based on it. There's not much to add by increasing the dimensions just using the same technique as before, but we will cover the broadness with the format; saying 5-D is quite vague as it just says the number of total dimensions but not the number of spatial or time dimensions alone. We'll treat them as being "different," but they are essentially "connected" in the universe, acting with each other to define its "rules." You may have seen before that I used "D" and added "T" to specify the amount of each previously, which will be used for this model. When it comes to spatial dimensions, add a variable (that can be incremented) in front of the set, and for time dimensions, you only need to signify what value it may be (1-T, 2-T, etc.).

Formatting

This section will give a summary of the structure of the model in a simple and simplified manner.

Binary

- **0**, low chance and intensity of vibration due to less energy present.
- **1**, high chance and intensity of vibration due to more energy being present.
- **-1**, a “buffer” and equilibrium in space.

Strings

A matrix to represent a string or part in “space” $\rightarrow [0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, \dots]$

Strings are extremely long but are finite. A dark set $\rightarrow [-1, -1, -1, -1, -1, \dots]$

1-D Infinitely thin but also extremely long (x),

2-D A plane in space (x, y), **3-D** A cube in space (x, y, z)

n-D m-T = (n variables (spatial); m variables (time)) = $(x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n; t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_m)$

E.g. 4-D 2-T = (x, y, z, a; t_1, t_2)

1-D $\rightarrow [1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1]$ (A string), $[-1, -1, -1, -1]$ (Dark set),

$[0, -1, 1, 0, -1, 1]$ (Ungrouped fluctuations)

2-D → 1. [0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, ...]

2. [1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 1, ...]

3. [0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, ...]

...

3-D → 1A. [...]; 1B. [...]; 1C. [...]; ...

2A. [...]; 2B. [...]; 2C. [...]; ...

3A. [...]; 3B. [...]; 3C. [...]; ...

...

Higher dimensions should follow this pattern.

Discussion

We have made a few assumptions for this model to work: Firstly, we assume that dark energy and dark matter are connected, just as energy and regular matter are. Secondly, we assume that dark energy is the ground state in the universe due to its abundance and properties, which we aren't completely sure of yet. Thirdly, we assume that strings can be accurately represented to a certain degree using 1s and 0s for the intensities in the frequency. Lastly, we assume that different universes with different dimensions exist.

These assumptions were made based on an educated guess of other laws of the universe, used as a reference point. The validity of these assumptions shall be left up to debate, as there are currently no proofs that can prove or disprove them.

Regarding the uses of this thought experiment, it is simply meant to be used as a tool for understanding at an introductory level, not completely accurate but the simplest interpretation.

However, this is not intended to be connected with actual formulas, only the structure.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have talked about string theory and binary digits, mixing both to create a model to represent strings as a matrix, emphasising the intensities in the string using binary digits, and including dark energy as the ground state in the model. We then talked about the interactions of the string, creating particles and antiparticles, which then collide and cancel out, releasing a gamma ray representing quantum fluctuations in space. And finally, we talked about dimensions, their respective interpretations, and vagueness when dealing with them.

There're a few limitations with this model. Being simplified to a very complex field means that it loses its accuracy to a certain degree, but regardless, it is still an easy way to interpret string theory to allow more people to take an interest. As we gain more information from research over time this model may be modified to better fit the truth.

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